

Paper 11

A STUDY ON THE INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN EMPLOYEE RETENTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AVIATION INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Employee retention involves the effective management of organization through retaining eminent work force thereby considered to be the mastery of managing resources. Every organization invests its time and money to groom newly recruited and developing them to be an efficient employee. Losing a trained employee is a great loss for any organization. Employee retention is an art of using various unique techniques to influence an employee to stay in an organization for the longer duration of his service. Hertz Berg's and Maslow's in their theory have quoted about factors influencing for individual growth and development. Aviation business is facing a serious problem of high attrition since long due to the shortage of technical, non-technical and other skilled professionals. The retention strategies in business help in reducing employee turnover, recruitment and training cost. It also preserves talent and organizational knowledge. The businesses have inculcated trending tools of competitive salary, fringe benefits, skilled hiring, work life balance, career development, friendly work culture, employee engagement, branding, bonding, open communication, work from home, flexible working, fancy designation to demark employee retention. Innovative strategies for employee retention in aviation sector are the need of the day. This paper highlights upon various modern tools and strategies on employee retention with special reference to aviation industry emphasizing on out of the box benefits to its employees.

Keywords: Employee Retention, Efficient Employee, Techniques, Aviation Industry, benefits

1. INTRODUCTION

In simple words, Employee retention means the act of maintaining and sustaining the existing employment relationship for a longer period. It is considered as the biggest ability of any organization, which is essential for organizational success. It is a dynamic process where the employer encourages their employees to remain with the organization for the maximum period of time through innovative retention strategies. The success of any organization is determined by the productivity and effort of its employees as well as the satisfaction that they obtain from their jobs, fellow workers, management, work environment, the rewards system

and the career growth opportunity. The retention of the skilled employee is the major concern of every manager. Maintaining the skills of employees' in order to maintain a competitive edge is becoming very essential in the world of Globalization and Privatization. The process of retention starts from recruitment, hiring the right candidate for the right job is the prime requisite in employee retention. With the introduction of low-cost carriers, aviation industry witnessed a dramatic change and growth during the past decades, which revolutionized the aviation business. But meantime retention of skilled human resource in the aviation business became a challenging task due to various reasons. As per the latest studies, 50 per cent of the employees would leave their current job for better financial and non-financial benefits. "Employee retention is a voluntary act and process of building and promoting a positive working environment by engaging employees for a long period with the organization for mutual benefit"

2. SCOPE OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION

The Cabin crew job has become one of the most stressful occupations due to the perpetual pressure carried while performing duties both on the ground and on board but, the airlines adopting strategies of cost-cutting considers its employees like machines without providing job security, reduced wage and long hours of work [1]. The lack of talented-workers and the risk of losing their skilled, experienced human-resources are considered as the key issues of modern organizations [2]. Abraham Maslow's need hierarchy theory emphasizes on the need of companies to consider factors like employees' health, job security, and remuneration. When employees know that their employer care about their health and that their job is guaranteed, they will be bound to the company [3]. The Airline companies are continuously losing on the skilled employees and are facing a big challenge in retaining these employees. Airlines recruit the most qualified and skilled candidates, retaining these highly skilled employees are a bigger challenge. The employee joins an organization with lot of expectations and employees tend to leave the organization sooner in case if the job in a particular airline company is not meeting their expectation. It is the responsibilities of the managers to examine and identify the reason for retention and formulation of suitable retention strategy. Herzberg's theory focuses on factors like motivator and hygiene factors which determine the rate of employee retention. The motivator factors such as recognition, achievement, work, growth, and advancement will lead to employee satisfaction whereas the hygiene elements like factors include a relationship with management, supervision, remuneration, relationship with colleagues, working conditions and the rules and policies of the company will cause dissatisfaction [4].

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The core objective of this study is to understand the reasons behind the deficiency of qualified professionals in Aviation Industry. It finds the reason behind attrition, analyze employee retention strategies and examining the changes in the emerging trends to retain aviation work force. The paper also examines the sensitive factors like ergonomics, workplace sexual harassment, racial discrimination, technology, HR Policies and its impact on employees in an organization.

4. ATTRITION IN AVIATION INDUSTRY

Turnover of key employees will have dangerous consequences on organization's objectives. With the changing environment, the needs, requirements and expectations of the

employees also changes. So it is the responsibility of every organization to hold their employees tightly because they are capable of building and breaking of any organization. Factors like lack of professionalism, corruption, over involvement of external bodies such as Government and other Agencies, behavior of co-worker will also lead to employee attrition. These factors have an effect on the attitude of the employees resulting in frustration, causing them to change jobs for a better environment, and increasing turnover rates particularly in the aviation sector. Employee turnover issues could be reduced if these factors are paid due attention and managed properly.

5. BREAKTHROUGHS TOWARDS RETAINING EMPLOYEES

Identity of Airline Company is the prestige for its employees. The elements like organizational culture, reputation, benefits, opportunities for advancement will contribute to the brand image. Airlines recruits the most qualified and skilled candidates, retaining these highly skilled employees are a bigger challenge. The employee joins an organization with lot of expectations and employees tend to leave the organization in case of not meeting their expectation. This HR Policy must be conveyed to the employees to plans for the future to increase the employee commitment, personal productivity [5]. Competitive compensation is the most crucial factor of an employee retention strategy [6]. There is a positive relationship between employee retention and job security. Leadership styles effects retention factor. Increased workload creates poor work-life balance. Proper Performance Management System facilitate career development [7]. As the industry jobs are highly risky involving high rate of hazards, providing proper work environment will prevent attrition. The subcontracting for low-bid contractors are worsening the working conditions of baggage handlers, security, cabin cleaners, janitors, wheelchair attendants. The Airline Companies invest a huge amount to training programs to train with virtual reality technique to motivate employees to stick to their jobs [8]. The emergence of low cost career has adversely affected the overall hiring and compensation culture of the industry. The fancy designation is one of retention tools. The racial harassment is the crucial issue in modern working environment. Some organizations offers retention bonus to their employees. A culturally oriented leadership with embracing norms harms the retention [9]. Air Traffic Controlling job profile involves highly complex procedures resulting stress and fatigue hence these jobs are installed with latest know-how with training, job design etc. [10].

6. CONCLUSION

Employee retention has become a global agenda. Ergonomics consideration in Airline industry to increase employee retention rate are lighting, tools and equipment, health and safety Issues, preventing back injuries, work style, stress, fatigue, shift, risk factors etc. Employee retention is a dynamic process, where technique used by the organization also changes with the time. Influential leadership behavior can win the trust and will bring satisfaction to the employees, which will further result in higher organizational commitment and higher level of retention [11]. This paper shows that the poor organization culture and non-effective HR policies are the major reason behind high attrition in recent years. By exploring the HR policies and strategies with innovative and progressive measures can retain its talents.

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